

TITLE: Longitudinal Power Doppler Ultrasonographic Assessment of Joint Inflammatory Activity in Early Rheumatoid Arthritis: Predictive Value in Disease Activity and Radiological Progression.

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Key words: Rheumatoid Arthritis, Ultrasound, Power Doppler

ABSTRACT

Objective: To evaluate the sensitivity to change of power Doppler (PD) ultrasound (US) assessment of joint inflammation and the predictive value of PD US parameters in disease activity and radiological outcome in patients with early rheumatoid arthritis (RA).

Methods: Forty two patients with early RA who started therapy with disease modifying antirheumatic drugs, underwent blinded sequential clinical, laboratory and US assessment (baseline, 3 months, 6 months, 1 year) as well as radiographic assessment (baseline and 1 year). For each patient 28 joint Disease Activity Score (DAS 28) was recorded at each visit. The presence of joint synovitis with grey scale US and intra-articular PD signal was investigated in 28 joints. Active synovitis (AS) was defined as intra-articular synovitis with PD signal. The joint count for AS (USJCAS), and an overall joint index for PD signal (USJIPD) were calculated. Sensitivity to change of PD US variables was assessed by estimating the smallest detectable difference (SDD) from the intraobserver variability.

Results: The SDD for USJCAS and USJIPD was lower than mean changes from baseline to 3, 6 months, and 1 year. Time integrated values of PD US parameters showed a highly significant correlation with DAS 28 after 1 year ($r=0.63$, $p<0.001$) and stronger correlation with radiographic progression ($r=0.59-0.66$, $p<0.001$) than clinical and laboratory parameters ($r<0.5$,).

Conclusion: PD US is a sensitive and reliable method for longitudinal assessment of inflammatory activity in early RA. PD US findings may have a predictive value in disease activity and radiographic outcome.

The accurate assessment of joint inflammation and sensitive monitoring of disease activity in rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is essential to evaluate the response to treatment and disease outcome (1). In early RA, synovitis appears to be the primary abnormality responsible for structural joint damage (2). In this case the monitoring of RA patients' therapy should focus on synovitis.

It is known that synovial inflammation consists of periarticular vasodilatation followed by synovial proliferation, which is accompanied by angiogenesis resulting in intra-articular blood vessel formation (3). Hypervascularization and angiogenesis of the synovial membrane are considered to be primary pathogenic mechanisms responsible for the invasive behavior of rheumatoid pannus (3-5). Therefore there is a relationship between joint inflammatory activity and synovial vascularization (6).

Joint synovitis has traditionally been assessed indirectly by means of inflammatory subjective clinical data and laboratory parameters. Imaging techniques such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and musculoskeletal ultrasound (US) are playing an increasingly important role in the evaluation and monitoring of patients with chronic inflammatory arthritis. Assessment of synovial inflammatory activity by MRI has shown a close correlation with histological findings (7,8). In addition, MRI findings have demonstrated a predictive value in structural joint damage in early RA (9,10). However, MRI is expensive, time consuming and not widely available for routine clinical use in many countries.

The greater resolution of superficial musculoskeletal structures offered by high-frequency transducers has promoted an increasing use of US in rheumatic diseases (11). US is a routinely available, non-invasive and relatively inexpensive bedside imaging method with high patient acceptability. This technique is more sensitive and reproducible than clinical evaluation in assessing joint inflammation (12-19). The main advantage of US over MRI is that all the peripheral joints can be examined as many times as required and at the time of consultation. This improves the accuracy of clinical evaluation. In addition, prosthetic joints do not interfere with US images.

Color Doppler (CD) and power Doppler (PD) US techniques detect synovial flow which is a sign of increased synovial vascularization (20). The presence of intra-articular CD/PD signal aids in distinguishing active synovitis from inactive intra-articular thickening (21-29). CD and PD findings have correlated with local clinical evaluation of joint inflammatory activity (13,22,23), overall clinical and biological inflammatory activity (19), MRI joint inflammatory findings (24,25,26), and histologic synovial vascularisation (27-29) in patients with RA .

Several studies have shown a significant reduction of joint inflammation evaluated by grey-scale and CD or PD US in a limited number of arthritic joints in patients treated in different ways (15,22,30-37). Nevertheless, to the best of our knowledge, there are no studies on the predictive value of longitudinal US joint assessment in the areas of disease activity, functional status, and radiologic progression in early RA.

The aim of this study was to demonstrate the sensitivity to change of overall PD US joint assessment and the predictive value of sequential PD US parameters in clinical, functional and radiological outcomes in patients with early RA who started treatment with disease modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs).

Materials and Methods

Forty two consecutive patients (11 male, 31 female) with early RA (joint symptoms for less than 1 year) according to the 1987 American Rheumatism Association criteria for RA (38), attending the outpatient rheumatologic clinic, and who started therapy with DMARDs were prospectively included. Mean (SD) age was 53.6 (14.1) years (interval 24-77) and mean disease duration was 6.8 (3.6) months (interval 1.5-12).

The patients underwent a clinical, laboratory, and PD US evaluation at baseline (24 hours within stating treatment with DMARDs), 3 months, 6 months, and 1 year. Radiographic assessment was performed at baseline and at 1 year of follow-up. Therapeutic decisions were taken without knowledge of the US findings.

The study was approved by the local ethics committee and informed consent was obtained from all patients before the study entry.

Clinical Assessment

The clinical evaluation was performed for all patients by the same rheumatologist (PC), blinded to the US and radiographic findings, and who was not involved in the treatment decisions.

The following data were recorded for each patient at the study entry: age, sex, symptom duration, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and corticosteroids received for RA before the entry, DMARDs prescribed, extra-articular involvement of RA and rheumatoid factor (immunoturbidimetric assay, Roche/Hitachi Systems, normal level: 0-15 UI/ml). Drugs received for RA, extra-articular RA involvement and joint surgery for RA were recorded at each visit.

At each visit, 28 joints (39) including bilateral glenohumeral, elbow, wrist, metacarpophalangeal (MCP), proximal interphalangeal (PIP) of hands, and knee were assessed for tenderness and swelling. Tender joint count (TJC) and swollen joint count (SJC) were recorded for each patient. A global pain intensity visual analogue scale (VASP; 0-100 mm), a visual analogue scale for the patient's overall assessment of disease activity (VASOA; 0-100 mm) and the functional status were also recorded at each visit. Functional ability was evaluated by a self-assessment Spanish version of the Health Assessment Questionnaire (HAQ) (40).

Laboratory assessment

Serum markers of inflammation, C- reactive protein (CRP) level (immunoturbidimetric assay, Roche/Hitachi Systems, normal level: 0-10 mg/L) and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) (measured by the Westergren method, VESMATIC 60, version 2.05, Menarini Laboratory, Barcelona, Spain, normal level: 10-20 mm 1 h) were recorded from each patient's laboratory test obtained within 48 h of each visit.

Disease activity assessment

Disease activity was assessed by calculating the 28 joint Disease Activity Score (DAS 28) for each patient at each visit (41).

US assessment

The patients underwent a US assessment within 30 minutes of each clinical evaluation, by a single rheumatologist experienced in US (EN) who was unaware of the clinical, laboratory, and radiographic findings and who was not involved in the treatment decisions. US was carried out without access to the previous visit results in order to reduce the possibility of bias. The patients were asked not to talk about their clinical symptoms to the US examiner.

A systematic grey-scale and PD US examination of the 28 joints clinically investigated was carried out with a commercially available real-time scanner (Logiq 500CL, General Electric Medical Systems, Japan) using multifrequency linear array transducers, 7-12 MHz.

The US scanning method is described in Table 1 (14,15,17,19,24,25,31,34,42,43). Joint synovitis was defined as the presence of intra-articular effusion and/or synovial hypertrophy. The presence of synovitis was identified in each joint as hypoechoic intra-articular material according to the criteria listed in Table I (19,43,36,42,44). Measurements were taken at the point where most capsular or joint recess distension was seen. Distances were measured using electronic calipers.

Synovial blood flow was evaluated by PD in each of the 28 joints. PD imaging was performed by selecting a region of interest that included the bony margins, articular space and a variable view of surrounding tissues (depending on the joint size). PD parameters were adjusted at the lowest permissible pulse repetition frequency (PRF) to maximise sensitivity. This setting resulted in PRF from 500 to 1,000 Hz depending on the joint scanned. Low wall filters were used. The dynamic range was 20-40 dB. Color gain was set just below the level at which color noise appeared underlying bone (no flow should be visualized at bony surface) This setting resulted in gains from 18 to 30 dB. Flow was additionally demonstrated in two planes and confirmed by pulsed-wave Doppler spectrum to exclude artefacts.

Active synovitis (AS) was defined as the presence of intra-articular synovitis with PD signal. Joint count for US AS (USJCAS) was obtained at each US assessment.

In addition, the intra-articular PD signal was graded on a semiquantitative scale from 0 to 3

(0=absence, no intraarticular flow; 1=mild, single vessel signal or isolated signals; 2=moderate, confluent vessels; 3=marked, vessel signals in more than half of the intra-articular area) during the US examination (19,22,28,30,37). An overall joint index for PD signal (USJIPD) (the sum of the PD signal scores obtained from each joint) was calculated at each US assessment.

Representative images of PD US findings are given in Figure 1.

Radiographic assessment

Postero-anterior films of the hands and antero-posterior films of the feet of the patients were made at baseline (within 10 days of the study entry) and at 1 year of follow-up. The radiographs were read twice with a minimum interval of 2 weeks, in chronological order by an independent observer (AC) who was blinded to patients' identity, clinical, laboratory, and US findings. Radiological damage was assessed according to the van der Heijde's modification of Sharp's method (45,46). This method measures erosions (score from 0 to 280) and joint space narrowing (JSN) (score from 0 to 168) in 44 different joints, and provides a sum score ranging from 0 to 448. As defined in the description of the scoring method, total scores could increase or be stable, but not decrease. Results were expressed as erosion score, JSN score, and total score.

The scores from the first assessment of baseline and final films were used for analysis with the clinical, laboratory, and US data. The intraobserver reliability was assessed by calculating the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) from both radiographic reading.

US intraobserver reliability

Intraobserver reliability of the US examination was evaluated by recording representative images of the 28 joints from one visit of 20 patients, randomly chosen, on a magnetic optical disk. The stored images were blindly read and scored for PD signal by the same rheumatologist who performed all the US examinations (EN) a minimum of 3 months after the corresponding real-time scanning.

Outcome variables

The DAS 28, the HAQ score, the radiographic erosion, JSN and total scores at 1 year along with

progression in the radiographic erosion, JSN and total scores from baseline to 1 year were considered the outcome variables.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS statistical software, version 8.0 (SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA). Quantitative variables (clinical, laboratory, US, and radiographic parameters) are given as mean, standard deviation (SD), and interval. Correlations between clinical, laboratory, US, and radiographic parameters were analyzed by Pearson or Spearman's rank correlation test according to the variable distribution. The course of the process variables was obtained by calculating time integrated values by the area under the curve (AUC) method (47). Any p value under 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

The sensitivity to change of the US variables was assessed by estimating the smallest detectable difference (SDD) (48). The intraobserver variability was obtained by calculating the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) (2-way mixed effects model, consistency definition) for joint count for AS and joint index for PD signal. The US intraobserver reliability was also evaluated using the unweighted kappa test and the overall agreement (defined as the percentage of observed exact agreements) for the grade of PD signal in each joint. Values of Kappa < 0.40 reflect poor agreement, between 0.40 and 0.75 fair to good agreement, and >0.75 excellent agreement (49).

Results

Patient characteristics

Complete follow-up data were obtained from 38 of the 42 patients included in the study. One patient attended only the baseline and 1 year visits, 1 patient did not attend the 6 month and 1 year visits, and 2 patients did not attend the 1 year visit. Available data from the 4 patients with incomplete follow-up were analyzed.

At the study entry, rheumatoid factor (RF) was positive in 30 (71.4%) patients and negative in 12 (28.6%). Positive RF mean value was 135 (160, 16-880) UI/ml.

Before the study entry, 27 (64.3%) patients had received oral corticosteroids for a mean of 1.6 (1.4, 0.2-6) months and 36 (85.7%) patients, NSAIDs for a mean of 4.2 (2.9, 1-12) months.

At inclusion, 41 patients started therapy with 1 DMARD and 1 patient with 2 DMARDs. Therapeutic regimens included antimalarial drugs (61.9%), methotrexate (28.6%), leflunomide (4.8%), sulfasalazine (4.8%), and gold salts (2.4%). Low doses (5-10 mg/day) of prednisone were prescribed to 30 (71.4%) patients and NSAIDs to 28 (66.7%).

After the 1 year follow-up, 31 patients were taking 1 DMARD and 7 patients a combination of DMARDs. The RA treatment consisted of antimalarial drugs (61.5%), methotrexate (41%), leflunomide (7.7%), sulfasalazine (5.1%), gold salts (2.6%), low doses (2.5-7.5 mg/day) of prednisone (66.7%), and NSAIDs (59%).

No patient had extra-articular RA involvement at baseline or at 1 year. Joint surgery for RA was not required for any patient during the study.

Clinical, laboratory, US and radiographic course.

Clinical, laboratory, and US parameters during followup are given in Table 2. Intra-articular PD signal was only present in joints with synovitis. The US examination of the 28 joints took about 20 minutes, not including documentation.

Bone erosions were detected in 19 (45.2%) patients at baseline and in 23 (59%) patients after 1 year. The mean radiographic erosion and JSN scores increased from 1.7 (3.2, 0-13) and 11.2 (9.8, 0-43) at baseline to 3.8 (6.3, 0-28) and 14.5 (11.1, 0-45) after 1 year. Seventeen (43.6%) patients showed progression in radiographic erosion score and 27 (69.2%) in JSN score at 1 year of follow-up.

Transversal correlation between US variables and disease activity and functional status

Table 2 shows the cross-sectional correlations between the US parameters and the DAS 28, the CRP level and the HAQ score at each visit. The USJCAS and USJIPD correlated significantly with the DAS 28 and the CRP level along the study. The correlation coefficients were higher at 6 months and 1 year than at baseline and 3 months of follow-up. There was a weakly significant correlation between the

US variables and the HAQ score at 3 and 6 months as well as at 1 year.

Intraobserver reliability and sensitivity to change of the US assessment

Intraobserver kappa values for the the US evaluation of each joint ranged from good to excellent (0.75- 1). The mean Kappa value (SD; interval) was 1 (0; 1-1) for glenohumeral PD signal, 0.75 (0.4; 0.49-1) for elbow PD signal, 0.94 (0.1; 0.87-1) for wrist PD signal, 0.91 (0.2; 0.47-1) for MCP PD signal, 1 (0; 1-1) for PIP of hands PD signal, and 0.87 (0.2; 0.73-1) for knee PD signal. Intraobserver US overall agreement ranged from 98 to 100%.

Intraobserver ICC was 0.99 (CI 95%, 0.99-0.99) for the USJCAS and 0.99 (CI 95%, 0.98-0.99) for the USJIPD. The SDD was 0.95 for the USJCAS and 1.61 for the USJIPD.

The mean (SD) change in USJCAS was 1.7 (3.8) from baseline to 3 months, 1.2 (3.1) from baseline to 6 months, and 2.1 (2.3) from baseline to 1 year. The mean (SD) change in USJIPD was 1.9 (5.3) from baseline to 3 months, 1.7 (3.6) from baseline to 6 months, and 2.6 (3.7) from baseline to 1 year.

Intraobserver reliability of the radiographic assessment

The ICC for the baseline films was 0.95 (95% confidence interval (CI)), 0.87 to 1) for the erosion score, 0.86 (95% CI, 0.74 to 0.98) for the JSN score, 0.85 (95% CI, 0.71 to 0.98) for the total score, and for the films taken after 1 year, 0.95 (95% CI, 0.89 to 1) for the erosion score, 0.82 (95% CI, 0.65 to 0.99) for the JSN score, 0.82 (95% CI, 0.65 to 0.98) for the total score.

Longitudinal correlation between US, clinical, and laboratory parameters and outcome variables

There was no correlation between changes in the US parameters and changes in the DAS 28 along the follow-up.

The correlations between the clinical, laboratory, functional, and US parameters at each visit and the DAS 28 and HAQ score at the following visit showed that the USJCAS and USJIPD were the strongest predictive variables of the disease activity at the following visit (Table 4). The VASP and HAQ score were the strongest predictors of the functional status at the following visit (Table 4).

Table 5 displays the correlations between the time integrated values of clinical, laboratory, functional and US parameters and the outcome variables. The time integrated values of USJCAS and USJIPD showed a stronger significant correlation with the progression in the radiographic erosion score, JSN score, and total score progression as well as the erosion and total scores at 1 year than the clinical, laboratory and functional parameters, including DAS 28. In addition, the time integrated values of the US parameters demonstrated a highly significant correlation with the DAS 28 after 1 year (Table 5). The time integrated US values did not correlated with the functional status at 1 year (Table 5).

There was not significant correlation between the baseline clinical, laboratory, functional and US parameters and the DAS28, the HAQ score and the radiographic scores at 1 year of follow-up.

Discussion

The development of new reliable methods for assessing synovial inflammation and response to treatment in RA is a challenge in daily practice and clinical trials and a relevant research field in Rheumatology. Within the last decade, there has been an increasing use of musculoskeletal US with CD or PD technique for evaluating joint inflammatory activity in patients with RA.

In our study, we chose a combination of grey scale (presence of joint effusion and/or synovial hypertrophy) and PD findings (presence and grade of intra-articular PD signal) as US variables reflecting active rheumatoid pannus. We found a significant transversal correlations between the PD US findings and standard measurements of RA inflammatory activity such as the DAS 28 and the CRP level while correlations between the PD US parameters and the HAQ score were weak to moderately significant at the follow-up. In a previous cross-sectional study on the comparison of grey-scale and PD US with global clinical and laboratory assessment of joint inflammation in RA, we also found a significant correlation between US parameters and disease activity markers such as the swollen joint count, the CRP level and the ESR (19). In contrast, there was no correlation between the US variables and the HAQ score. This discrepancy may be due to the longest disease duration (69.3 (58.29) months) that the patients included in the previous study had. In long-standing RA, HAQ indicates either disease activity or residual structural

joint damage while in early RA, functional status is more likely related to inflammatory activity. .

In keeping with our results, other studies have shown changes in CD or PD US findings associated with clinical and laboratory response to intra-articular corticosteroid injections (22,33,36), systemic corticosteroid therapy (30,32) and biologic agents (15,31,34,37) in chronic inflammatory arthritis. However, the sensitivity to change of any method should be demonstrated by calculating the intraobserver variation and the SDD between repeated measurements (50). Most of the previous longitudinal studies have not assessed the sensitivity to change of US parameters. Ribbens et al (15) and Fiocco et al (37) reported intraobserver coefficients of variation lower than the changes in PD findings. We obtained a lower SDD for the USJCAS and the USJIPD than the changes in these variables from baseline to 3 months, 6 months, and 1 year.

Although changes in PD US parameters and DAS28 were parallel along the study, we did not find significant correlation between them. Thus, PD US findings seem to be a measurement of disease activity independent of standard clinical and laboratory variables.

The active synovitis count and the synovial vascularization index obtained by PD US showed a stronger correlation with the disease activity at the following visit than the clinical, laboratory, and functional parameters, including the DAS 28. In addition, the cumulative PD US parameters of inflammatory activity over time demonstrated a high correlation with disease activity at 1 year and the strongest correlation with the radiographic damage progression as well as the radiographic erosion and total scores after 1 year of DMARDs therapy, in early RA patients. Since changes in the RA treatment along the study were based only in clinical and laboratory parameters, a predictive value of PD US findings in disease activity and radiological outcome may be accepted.

Taylor et al (35) have previously evaluated the prognostic value of US in RA in a recent randomized controlled trial of anti-TNF alpha therapy in early RA. They have demonstrated that the baseline synovial vascularization detected by PD in MCP joints correlated with the radiographic joint damage over the following year (35) in patients receiving only methotrexate as DMARD. In contrast, we

did not find significant correlation between the baseline clinical, laboratory, functional and PD US variables and the disease activity, functional status and radiographic damage at 1 year. The different therapeutic regimens prescribed for the patients during the follow-up may explain the lack of baseline predictors in our study.

The results of both studies can reflect the pathogenic destructive role of angiogenesis in the rheumatoid synovium (3-5). Therefore the detection of vascularization in early rheumatoid synovial proliferation by US PD could be considered a strong predictor of disease aggressiveness which would contribute to make treatment decisions.

Some limitations of our study should be mentioned. First, our study was conducted in accordance with daily clinical practice. Patients were treated with various DMARDs, oral corticosteroids and NSAIDs at a variable dosage during the study. Therapeutic decisions were taken without knowledge of the US findings. Thus, we could not compare the predictive value of PD US variables depending on the DMARD received, evaluate the potential role of different DMARDs in PD US parameters or study the effect of PD US findings in therapeutic decisions.

Moreover, the rheumatologist performing US scanning could not be completely unaware of patient's joint signs and symptoms. To avoid as much bias as possible, US examination was carried out in the dark and the patients were asked not to communicate with the US examiner.

The lack of standardization of US examination method and settings for PD can limit the use of this technique in research protocols. Some different methods have been used for assessing CD or PD findings such as semiquantitative signal scoring (15,22,30,36,37), color pixel counting (31,32,33,34,35) and resistive index calculating (33,34). We considered semiquantitative signal grading as the most suitable for clinical practice. In agreement with previous study (15,37), our intraobserver kappa values and ICC were very high for PD US parameters.

In addition, PD is extremely sensitive to tissue movement, especially at low PRF, which can result in "flash" artifacts. However, we used pulsed Doppler spectra as proof of the presence of vessels when the

images were doubtful.

In conclusion, our results suggest that US with PD technique is a sensitive and reliable method for longitudinal assessment of inflammatory activity in early RA, additional to current clinical and laboratory evaluation, in daily management and clinical trials. Furthermore, PD US inflammatory findings seem to have a predictive value in disease activity as well as radiographic outcome. The latter emphasizes the importance of taking into account PD US findings for therapeutic decisions in early RA.

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Tables

Table 1. Ultrasonographic scanning of joints and criteria of synovitis.

Glenohumeral joint. Posterior recess, transducer transversal to the humerus, shoulder in neutral position: maximum distance from the posterior labrum to the posterior infraspinatus and teres minor tendon (posterior capsule) greater than 3 millimeters (mm). Axillar recess, transducer longitudinal to the axilla, shoulder in 90° of abduction: maximum distance from the humeral profile to the capsule greater than 3 mm.

Elbow. Longitudinal and transversally, from the anterior recess with the joint in extension: maximum distance from the humeral capitulum or the coronoid fossa to the joint capsule greater than 2 mm.

Wrist (radiocarpal and midcarpal joint). Longitudinal and transversally, from the dorsal aspect with the joint in neutral position: maximum distance from the bones to the joint capsule greater than 2 mm .

Metacarpophalangeal and proximal interphalangeal joints of hands. Longitudinal and transversally, from the dorsal, medial and lateral view with the joint in extension: maximum distance from the articular bony margin to the joint capsule greater than 2 mm.

Knee. Longitudinal and transversally, from the suprapatellar recess, in a supine position, with the joint in 30° of flexion: maximum anterior-posterior diameter of the suprapatellar recess greater than 4 mm. Medial and lateral parapatellar recesses, transducer transversal to the patella, in a supine position, with the knee fully extended: maximum anterior-posterior diameter greater than 2 mm.

Table 2. Clinical, laboratory and US course.

Parameters	Baseline	3 months	6 months	12 months
	mean (SD; interval)	mean (SD; interval)	mean (SD; interval)	mean (SD; interval)
VASP	42.5 (30.5; 0-100)	34.4 (29.9; 0-100)	33 (30.9; 0-100)	34.9 (32.5; 0-100)
VASOA	56.5 (30; 0-100)	38.8 (36.2; 0-100)	42.7 (30.4; 0-100)	36.7 (31.8; 0-100)
TJC	4.8 (4.2; 0-17)	2.6 (3.4; 0-13)	2.1 (3.1; 0-13)	1.8 (2.4; 0-9)
SJC	5.5 (4.5; 0-20)	3.8 (3.9; 0-15)	4 (4.9; 0-23)	2.4 (3.4; 0-16)
ESR	25.5 (18; 4-81)	22.7 (16.5; 1-88)	27.3 (22; 5-113)	20.5 (12.7; 4-50)
CRP	12.8 (12.8; 2-65)	8.6 (8.6; 2-35)	14.5 (22.4; 2-113)	8.3 (8.5; 2-39)
DAS 28	4.6 (1.2; 1.9-7.2)	3.6 (1.3; 1.7-6.6)	3.7 (1.2; 1.7-7.1)	3.4 (1.1; 1.7-6.1)
HAQ	0.9 (0.7; 0-2.8)	0.6 (0.7; 0-2.4)	0.7 (0.7; 0-2.4)	0.6 (0.6; 0-2.3)
USJCAS	4 (4.5; 0-21)	2.3 (2.9; 0-12)	2.8 (4.1; 0-19)	1.9 (3.7; 0-14)
USJIPD	5.7 (6.4; 0-26)	3.8 (5.3; 0-25)	4 (6.3; 0-30)	3.1 (6.3; 0-23)

VASP, visual analogue scale for pain; VASOA, visual analogue scale for patient's overall assessment of disease activity; TCJ, tender joint count; SJC, swollen joint count; ESR, erythrocyte sedimentation rate; CRP, C- reactive protein; DAS 28, 28 joint Disease Activity Score; HAQ, Health Assessment Questionnaire; USJCAS, ultrasonographic joint count for active synovitis; USJIPD, ultrasonographic joint index for power Doppler signal.

Table 3. Transversal correlation between ultrasonographic variables, DAS 28, HAQ, and CRP at each visit.

US variables	Baseline			3 months			6 months			1 year		
	DAS28	HAQ	CRP	DAS 28	HAQ	CRP	DAS 28	HAQ	CRP	DAS 28	HAQ	CRP
USJCAS	0.43**	ns	0.33*	0.43**	0.38*	0.45**	0.57***	0.35*	0.62***	0.59***	0.41*	0.57***
USJIPD	0.48**	ns	0.32*	0.43**	ns	0.52**	0.61***	0.35*	0.68***	0.56***	0.39*	0.57***

*= p<0,05; **=p<0,01; ***=p<0,001; ns= non-significant

US, ultrasonographic; DAS 28, 28 joint Disease Activity Score; HAQ, Health Assessment Questionnaire; CRP, C- reactive protein; USJCAS, ultrasonographic joint count for active synovitis; USJIPD, ultrasonographic joint index for power Doppler signal.

Table 4. Correlation between clinical, laboratory and ultrasonographic variables at each visit and disease activity (DAS 28) and functional ability (HAQ) at the following visit.

Baseline	DAS 28	HAQ	3 months	DAS 28	HAQ	6 months	DAS 28	HAQ
	3 months	3 months		6 months	6 months		12 months	12 months
VASP	0.37*	0.60***	VASP	0.46**	0.47**	VASP	0.49**	0.48**
VASOA	0.34*	ns	VASOA	0.39*	0.34*	VASOA	0.32*	0.37*
TJC	ns	ns	TJC	0.32*	Ns	TJC	0.42**	0.39*
SJC	0.33*	0.32*	SJC	0.35*	Ns	SJC	0.39*	ns
ESR	ns	ns	ESR	0.39*	0.34*	ESR	0.46**	ns
CRP	0.38*	0.33*	CRP	0.54***	0.50**	CRP	0.33*	ns
DAS 28	0.39*	0.35*	DAS 28	0.56***	0.45**	DAS 28	0.56***	0.35*
HAQ	0.33*	0.58***	HAQ	0.48**	0.49**	HAQ	0.53**	0.63***
USJCAS	0.45**	0.31*	USJCPD	0.57***	0.39*	USJCPD	0.58***	ns
USJIPD	0.46**	0.31*	USJIPD	0.60***	0.47**	USJIPD	0.58***	ns

*= p<0,05; **=p<0,01; ***=p<0,001; ns= non-significant

DAS 28, 28 joint Disease Activity Score; HAQ, Health Assessment Questionnaire; VASP, visual analogue scale for pain; VASOA, visual analogue scale for patient's overall assessment of disease activity; TCJ, tender joint count; SJC, swollen joint count; ESR, erythrocyte sedimentation rate; CRP,

C- reactive protein; USJCAS, ultrasonographic joint count for active synovitis; USJIPD, ultrasonographic joint index for power Doppler signal.

Table 5. Correlation between time-integrated value of clinical, laboratory, and ultrasonographic variables and disease activity (DAS 28), functional ability (HAQ), and radiologic outcome at 1 year of follow-up.

TIV	DAS 28 1 year	HAQ 1 year	Erosion score progression	JSN score progression	Total score progresión	Erosion score 1 year	JSN score 1 year	Total score 1 year
VASP	0.58***	0.65***	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
VASOA	0.51**	0.58***	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
TJC	0.50**	0.50**	0.44**	ns	0.36*	ns	ns	ns
SJC	0.45**	ns	0.47**	ns	0.46**	0.40*	ns	ns
ESR	0.49**	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
CRP	0.49**	ns	ns	0.35*	ns	ns	ns	ns
DAS 28	0.75***	0.49**	0.44**	ns	0.40*	0.34*	ns	0.35*
HAQ	0.66***	0.82***	0.38*	ns	0.36*	ns	ns	ns
USJCAS	0.63***	ns	0.66***	0.37*	0.61***	0.66***	ns	0.50**
USJIPD	0.63***	ns	0.62***	0.41*	0.59***	0.62***	ns	0.48**

*= p<0,05; **=p<0,01; ***=p<0,001; ns= non-significant

TIV, time-integrated value; DAS 28, 28 joint Disease Activity Score; HAQ, Health Assessment Questionnaire; JSN, joint space narrowing; VASP, visual analogue scale for pain; VASOA, visual

analogue scale for patient's overall assessment of disease activity; TCJ, tender joint count; SJC, swollen joint count; ESR, erythrocyte sedimentation rate; CRP, C- reactive protein; USJCAS, ultrasonographic joint count for active synovitis; USJIPD, ultrasonographic joint index for power Doppler signal.

Figure Legends

Figure 1. Longitudinal sonographic image of wrist synovitis shows mild (A), moderate (B), and marked (C) PD color signal. Long= longitudinal; R= radius.